

Analyzing the Health Screening Results of Primary School Students: The Sample of X

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ABSTRACT

Background and Objectives: This study aimed to evaluate the health screening results of students in three public primary schools and to determine the changes over time.

Methods: The population of the study consisted of 1192 students studying in the first-fourth grades. The data of the study were collected with the Student Health Record form (5 sections) created by the researchers as a result of a literature review. In the evaluation of the data, number and percentage distributions were used.

Results: As a result of the health screenings conducted in two different periods, 2022-2023 academic year and 2023-2024 academic year, it was determined that the weight percentile values of the students decreased from 53.2% to 36.5% for those aged 75 and over and increased from 36.8% to 44.1% for those aged 25 to 74. It was determined that the height percentile values of the students aged 25 to 74 increased from 33.8% to 38.5%. Among the students who underwent health screening, those with systolic blood pressure values between 80-130 mmHg increased from 98.9% to 99.4%. In the 2022-2023 academic year, it was found that 70.7% of the students had visual acuity between 0.8 and 1.0 in the right eye, and 70.8% had visual acuity between 0.8 and 1.0 in the left eye. In the 2023-2024 academic year, 69.8% of the students had visual acuity between 0.8 and 1.0 in the right eye and 68.5% had visual acuity between 0.8 and 1.0 in the left eye. Among the students who underwent health screening, those who brushed their teeth in the evening increased from 73.1% to 79.7%.

Conclusion: The health screening results revealed changes within two semesters, and these changes were found to be positive. It can be stated that the realization rates of healthy lifestyle behaviors in students increased through health screenings.

KEYWORDS: health behavior, child health, health promotion

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INTRODUCTION

School childhood is an important period in terms of growth and development, and it is seen that the problems that arise in this period continue to have lifelong effects (Dıgrak, Ozturk-Eyimaya, Zengin, & Tezel, 2020). Due to the rapid physical growth and development of school-age children, their need for nutrients increases. The growth and development process requires more protein, minerals, and vitamins for the construction of new tissues and energy. The foods consumed must be in sufficient quantity and of good quality in order to meet all energy needs and to ensure adequate and balanced nutrition. Meals should not be skipped, and foods should be

consumed in three main meals and one or two snacks. During this period, bone mass increases, and there are changes in lifestyle and food intake. This affects both nutrient intake and meal patterns of children (Baysal, 2009).

Behaviors that will continue throughout life are also based in this period. The school environment plays a crucial role in reinforcing and establishing healthy eating habits. The school, as the first social place where school-age children interact and establish social relationships after their families, constitutes the most important element in the social structure (Akgul & Ergun, 2021). The school environment has an important place in providing children with the knowledge,

Analyzing the Health Screening Results of Primary School Students: The Sample of X

skills, and behaviors necessary to prevent diseases that may occur in the short and long term by providing children with positive habits related to adequate and balanced nutrition. The habits gained during this period, when lifelong behaviors are formed to a great extent, form the basis of permanent habits in adulthood (Sahinoz, Sahinoz, & Kivanc, 2017).

It is also widely known that some nutrition-related chronic diseases, such as obesity, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, some types of cancer, stroke, gout, and arthritis, are of childhood origin. In their study, Akcan et al. (2023) reported that 84.2% of schools had at least one student with a chronic disease, and diabetes was one of the three most common chronic diseases. Adequate and balanced nutrition is necessary for the prevention of diseases. Children who do not have adequate and balanced nutrition have a weak immune system, lack resistance to diseases, get sick frequently, have a severe prognosis, and their school success decreases due to absenteeism. In the study of Akcan et al. (2023), it was observed that more than half of the students diagnosed with the disease experienced problems such as a decrease in course success and an increase in school absenteeism. Consequently, importance should be given to the nutrition of children in this period in order to increase school success, reduce the cost of education and training by reducing grade repetitions, and prepare the basis for future generations to be healthier and stronger (Akder, Meseri, & Cakiroglu, 2018; Yehuda, Rabinovitz, & Mostofsky, 2006). The "Global Targets 2025 to improve maternal, infant, and young child nutrition" envisage no increase in the prevalence of mild obesity in childhood (WHO, 2014). In a study of children aged 6 to 9 years with the participation of 21 countries in Europe, it was pointed out that obesity is a serious public health problem today, and it was emphasized that early diagnosis and treatment of this problem is very important (Spinelli et al., 2019). In their study, Ozsoy et al. (2020) conducted to determine the prevalence of obesity in primary school children, it was found that 7,7% of children were overweight and 8,8% were obese (Ozsoy, Kalkim, & Sert, 2020).

While all school personnel have duties in the early detection of physical, behavioral, social, and academic problems of students, school health nurses also have some responsibilities. "Health screenings" offered in school health programs for raising healthy generations are among the building blocks of basic health services and are one of the ways that school nurses frequently apply (Acık, Deveci, Turacı-Celik, & Karaaslan, 2006). The aim of school health screenings is not only to diagnose diseases early but also to cure them, to treat them, and if they cannot be treated, to stop the progression of the disease in the early period and to contribute to the better health of children in the future. The scope, frequency, tests, and methods used in the evaluation of health screenings vary according to the needs of the community, the health service system, and the facilities of school health services. Within the scope of school health screenings, vision, hearing, height, body weight, scoliosis, oral and dental health, and blood

pressure screenings are among the recommended basic health screenings (Kırag & Bayık-Temel, 2016). There are studies on school health screenings in the literature, and their necessity is shown. Students come to school ready to learn, so health education given at schools can have an effective role in individuals having healthy behavioral habits throughout their lives (Dıgrak, Ozturk-Eyimaya, Zengin, & Tezel, 2020). Therefore, it is thought that the planned study will contribute to improving the health of schoolchildren, who constitute the majority of society. This study was conducted to evaluate the health screening results of students in three public primary schools and to determine the changes over time.

Research questions;

1. How are the height-weight health screening results of the students in primary school?
2. How are the vital signs health screening results of the students in primary school?
3. How are the vision health screening results of primary school students?
4. How are the hair and scalp health screening results of primary school students?
5. How have the health screening results of primary school students changed over time?

METHOD

Type of Research: This descriptive study was conducted on students from three primary schools in XXX in two periods from March 2023 to May 2023 and from March 2024 to May 2024.

Population/Sample of the Research: The population of the study consisted of 1192 students studying in the first, second, third and fourth grades. The sample of the study consisted of 1112 (93.28%) of these students in the first semester and 1090 (91.44%) in the second semester. The study data were collected by the researchers through the health screenings conducted by the third-year students of the Nursing Department of the Faculty of Health Sciences of a state university within the scope of the Public Health Nursing course. The students who took part in the collection of the study data were trained on height-weight measurements, the use of Snellen and Ishihara tables, ptosis, strabismus, and scalp evaluations.

Dependent-Independent Variables: The dependent variable of the study is the health screening results of the students. There is no independent variable.

Data Collection Tools: The data of the study were collected with the Student Health Record form (5 sections) created by the researchers as a result of a literature review. During the study, height, weight, blood pressure and pulse rate measurements, visual acuity, strabismus, color blindness, ptosis, and scalp dandruff, shedding, scarring, and lice were evaluated. The screening results of each student were recorded on the prepared forms, and the list of students with suspected health problems was reported to the school administration so that their families could be informed.

Analyzing the Health Screening Results of Primary School Students: The Sample of X

Screenings were conducted in a suitable room provided by the school administration. After the screenings, interviews were held with the school administration to determine the health education topics that were needed, and health trainings were provided for primary school students by third year students of the Department of Nursing, Faculty of Health Sciences of a state university.

Evaluation of Data: The data were evaluated using the SPSS 21.00 package program. In the evaluation of the data, number and percentage distributions were used.

Ethical Aspect of Research: Institutional permission was obtained from Provincial Directorate of National Education, and ethics committee approval was obtained from XXX (Decision No: 2022/03-05). An 'Informed Voluntary Consent Form' was completed by the parents of each participant who agreed to participate in the study.

RESULTS

Health screenings were conducted for 1112 students studying in three primary schools in XXX in the 2022-2023 academic years. As a result of the health screenings, it was determined that 53.2% of the students' weight percentile values were 75 and above, 36.8% were between 25-74, and 9.6% were between 3-24. It was determined that 59.8% of the students' height percentile values were 75 and above, 33.8% were between 25-74, and 6.1% were between 3-24. As a result of the health screenings, 98.7% of the students had a pulse rate between 60-120, 1.1% above 120 and 0.2% below 60. The systolic blood pressure values of 98.9% of the students were between 80-130 mmHg, 1.1% were above 130 mmHg. Diastolic blood pressure values of 97.1% of the students were between 50-85 mmHg and 2.9% were above 85 mmHg.

Health screening of 1090 students studying in three primary schools in XXX in the 2023-2024 academic years was performed. As a result of the health screenings, it was determined that 36.5% of the students' weight percentile values were 75 and above, 44.1% were between 25-74 and 19.4% were between 3-24. It was determined that 48.1% of the students' height percentile values were 75 and above, 38.5% were between 25-74 and 13.4% were between 3-24. As a result of the health screenings, 33.5% of the students' pulse rates were between 60-120, 1.2% were above 120 and 65.3% were below 60. The systolic blood pressure values of 99.4% of the students were between 80-130 mmHg, 0.6% were above 130 mmHg. Diastolic blood pressure values of 96.6% of the students were between 50-85 mmHg and 3.4% were above 85 mmHg (Table 1).

As a result of the health screenings of 1112 students studying in the 2022-2023 academic years, it was determined that 90.3% of the students did not wear glasses and 9.7% of the students wore glasses. Visual acuity was between 0.8 and 1.0 in the right eye (70.7%) and between 0.8 and 1.0 in the left eye (70.8%). As a result of the health screenings of 1090 students studying in the 2023-2024 academic years, it was determined that 92% of the students did not wear glasses and

8% of the students wore glasses. In visual acuity, 69.8% of the students had visual acuity between 0.8 and 1.0 in the right eye and 68.5% had visual acuity between 0.8 and 1.0 in the left eye (Table 2).

As a result of the health screenings of 1112 students studying in the 2022-2023 academic years, it was determined that 33.3% of the students brush their teeth less than 2 times a day and 66.7% brush their teeth more than 2 times a day. It was determined that 69.3% of the students brushed their teeth in the morning and 30.7% did not brush their teeth; 19.1% brushed their teeth at noon and 80.9% did not brush their teeth; 73.1% brushed their teeth in the evening and 26.9% did not brush their teeth. As a result of the health screenings, 85.4% of the students did not have dandruff, 93.8% did not have hair loss, 99.7% did not have scars, and 100% did not have lice. It was determined that 14.6% of the students had dandruff, 6.2% had hair loss, and 0.3% had scars.

As a result of the health screenings of 1090 students studying in the 2023-2024 academic years, it was determined that 38.3% of the students brush their teeth less than 2 times a day and 61.7% brush their teeth 2 or more times a day. It was determined that 66.4% of the students brushed their teeth in the morning and 33.6% did not brush their teeth; 15.9% brushed their teeth at noon and 84.1% did not brush their teeth; 79.7% brushed their teeth in the evening and 20.3% did not brush their teeth. As a result of the health screenings, 86.7% of the students did not have dandruff, 98.9% did not have hair loss, 98.7% did not have scars, and 99.5% did not have lice. It was determined that 13.3% of the students had dandruff, 1.1% had hair loss, 1.3% had scars, and 0.5% had lice (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

Despite the increase in the number of elderly people in Turkey's population in recent years, the number of children is considerably higher than the total population compared to other countries. As of the end of 2023, Turkey's population was 85 million 372 thousand 377 people, of which 22 million 206 thousand 34 were children; 51.3% of children were boys and 48.7% were girls. According to the United Nations definition, the child population, which includes the 0-17 age group, constituted 48.5% of the total population in 1970, while this rate was 41.8% in 1990 and 26.0% in 2023. Based on Turkey's population projections, the child population ratio is expected to be 25.6% in 2030, 23.3% in 2040, 20.4% in 2060, and 19.0% in 2080 (TurkStat, 2023).

The World Health Organization estimates that in 2022, an estimated 160 million (8.2%) of children and adolescents aged 5-19 years are living with obesity, and this number has increased by 130 million (4-fold) from 1990 to 2022 (WHO, 2024). The weight percentiles of the students included in the study were found to have decreased from 53.2% to 36.5% for those with a weight percentile of 75 and above. It is thought that the healthy nutrition education given to the students in the sample group was effective in this change. Likewise, in

Analyzing the Health Screening Results of Primary School Students: The Sample of X

the study conducted by Kostu et al. 21.6% of the weight percentile values were between 85-95 (Kostu et al., 2024). In Yılmaz and Babacan's (2020) study, when body mass index was calculated in students referred to family medicine for school-age follow-up, 48.15% were found to be outside normal values, and obesity was found in 10.19% of the students. Another study conducted in the United States found that the obesity rate of children aged 6-11 years was 18.4% (Halen et al., 2017). In a different study investigating the incidence and risk factors of obesity in primary school children, it was determined that 11.1% of the students were overweight and 7.5% were obese (Savashan, Sari, Aydoğan, & Erdal, 2015).

According to TurkStat (2023), eye-related problems (8.8%) are among the most common diseases in children aged 7-14 years. It can be stated that the rate of glasses use among the 2202 students who underwent vision screening within the scope of the study decreased from 9.7% to 8%. In visual acuity, it was found that the rate of visual acuity between 0.8 and 1.0 in the right eye decreased from 70.7% to 69.8%, and the rate of visual acuity between 0.8 and 1.0 in the left eye decreased from 70.8% to 68.5%. Based on the total number of students, it can be stated that 4.1% of the students have color blindness. In a study conducted in Ankara with a similar age group sample, it was determined that 8% of the students had visual defects. In the same study, 0.7% of students were found to have color blindness (Dıgrak, Ozturk-Eyimaya, Zengin, & Tezel, 2020). According to school-age follow-ups conducted in a family medicine unit in Ankara, 13.66% of students had visual impairment (Yılmaz & Babacan, 2020). In another study conducted with a similar age group in the Aegean region, 8% of students were thought to have suspected visual defects (Kırak & Bayık-Temel, 2016). In a study conducted with the same age group in Eskisehir, 10.5% of the students were found to have visual defects (Kalyoncu et al., 2011). Examining the studies conducted in different countries, 5.2% of students in a study conducted with primary school students in Ethiopia (Woldeamanuel et al., 2020), 6.4% of students in another similar study conducted in Sudan (Alrasheed et al., 2016), 2.7% in Brazil (Salomao et al., 2008), and 7.7% in China (Pi et al., 2012) were found to have visual defects. In the literature, it is seen that there are different results regarding the visual impairment of primary school students. It is thought that this difference may be due to the sample age and number, study type and visual acuity assessment technique. As children aged fifteen years and younger constitute the risky population in terms of visual acuity defects and blindness (WHO, 2017), public health nurses can contribute to the early diagnosis of visual defects and the protection of eye health in this framework through screenings in schools.

It is stated that dental problems in school-age children cause learning and attention difficulties, increase school absenteeism, and negatively affect eating and drinking, growth and development, speech, and socialization (Sisko &

Daghan, 2022). Therefore, it is quite important to protect oral and dental health. Brushing teeth regularly is one of the behaviors that protect oral and dental health. Within the scope of the study, it was found that the rate of students brushing their teeth 2 or more times a day decreased from 66.7% to 61.7%, the rate of morning tooth brushing decreased from 69.3% to 66.4%, the rate of noon tooth brushing decreased from 19.1% to 15.9%, and the rate of evening tooth brushing increased from 73.1% to 79.7%. An evaluation of the tooth brushing habits of third and fourth grade primary school students in Elazığ showed that 69.6% of the students brushed their teeth two or three times a day, and the majority of the students had good oral and dental health (Turan, Bozkurt, & Erdogan, 2022). In another study conducted with 120 children in Istanbul, it was found that 86% of the students brushed their teeth two or more times a day (Colakoglu & Has, 2015). Among primary school students living in rural areas in Istanbul, it was reported that 58.4% sometimes, 35.3% every day, and 6.4% never brush their teeth. In the same study, 55.5% of the students brush their teeth immediately after meals, 29.6% in the morning, and 14.8% before going to sleep at night (Peker et al., 2017). In another study conducted with school-age children with high socioeconomic status in Diyarbakır, the rate of students who regularly brush their teeth was 76.3% (Toktas et al., 2021). According to the Turkey Oral and Dental Health Profile Research Report (2018), 20.2% of children aged 5 and 21.0% of children aged 12 brush their teeth 2 or more times a day. In another multicenter study conducted in India, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Yemen, it was reported that the rates of paying attention to oral hygiene and tooth brushing (twice a day) in the 9-12 age group were moderate and 42.4%, respectively (Halawany et al., 2015). It is observed that daily tooth brushing rates in children vary in the literature. It is thought that this difference may be due to the age range of the sample group in the studies, the place where the studies were conducted, and the socioeconomic or sociocultural characteristics of these places.

The rate of dandruff in students' hair decreased from 14.6% to 13.3% and the rate of hair loss decreased from 6.2% to 1.1%. The rate of scarring increased from 0.3% to 1.3% and the rate of lice increased from 0.3% to 1.3% and 0.5%, respectively. In a study conducted with 785 primary school students in Manisa, 9.4% of the students were found to have lice. The same study reported that lice and dandruff were more common among female students than male students (Inanir et al., 2002). Another study conducted with schoolchildren and adolescents in Hong Kong revealed that dandruff was very common among students (Fung and Lo, 2000). Skin diseases are very common among children. Unfortunately, the number of studies on this subject is too limited. Most researchers are reluctant to examine skin diseases, and problems in primary school children. However, it is obvious that socio-economic status is related to skin diseases as in many other diseases. It is stated that infectious

Analyzing the Health Screening Results of Primary School Students: The Sample of X

diseases and morbidity rates are higher in societies with poor socio-economic status (WHO, 2000). In particular, infectious skin diseases are closely related to socio-economic status. It is stated that this situation is more common in individuals living in poor societies (Inanir et al., 2002).

CONCLUSION

It is known that habits acquired during childhood are transferred to adulthood. For this reason, health screenings should be carried out regularly in school-age children in order to ensure early diagnosis and treatment of diseases in childhood and to postpone or completely prevent the practice of habits that are harmful to health. As a result of health screenings and interventions by school/public health nurses, it may be possible to develop healthy lifestyle behaviors in students. School health nurses can serve the purpose of protecting and improving child health through health screenings and evidence-based interventions.

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LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY: The study data are limited to XXX province and cannot be generalized to all primary schools.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: There is no conflict of interest between the authors

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Analyzing the Health Screening Results of Primary School Students: The Sample of X

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Table 1. Weight, Height, Blood Pressure, and Pulse Rate of the Students

	Classifications	2022-2023 Period		2023-2024 Period	
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Weight Percentile	3-24	107	9,6	211	19,4
	25-74	411	36,8	481	44,1
	75 and above	594	53,2	398	36,5
Height Percentile	3-24	68	6,1	146	13,4
	25-74	377	33,8	420	38,5
	75 and above	667	59,8	524	48,1
Pulse	Under 60	2	0,2	712	65,3
	60-120	1098	98,7	365	33,5
	Over 120	12	1,1	13	1,2
Systolic Blood Pressure	80-130	1100	98,9	1084	99,4
	Over 130	12	1,1	6	0,6
Diastolic Blood Pressure	50-85	1080	97,1	1053	96,6
	Over 85	32	2,9	37	3,4
TOTAL		1112	100,0	1090	100,0

Analyzing the Health Screening Results of Primary School Students: The Sample of X

Table 2. Some Eye and Vision Related Conditions of the Students

	2022-2023 Period		2023-2024 Period	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Wearing Glasses	108	9,7	87	8
Not Wearing Glasses	1004	90,3	1003	92
Right Eye Visual Acuity is 0.1-0.7 (There is a Problem)	326	29,3	329	30,2
Right Eye Visual Acuity 0,8-1.0 (No Problem)	786	70,7	761	69,8
Left Eye Visual Acuity is 0,1-0,7 (There is a Problem)	325	29,2	343	31,5
Left Eye Visual Acuity 0,8-1.0 (No Problem)	787	70,8	747	68,5
Strabismus	16	1,4	6	0,5
Non-Strabismus	1096	98,6	1084	99,5
Right Eye with Ptosis	5	0,4	0	0
Right Eye Without Ptosis	1107	99,6	1051	100
Left Eye with Ptosis	10	0,9	0	0
Left Eye Without Ptosis	1102	99,1	1051	100
Right Eye with pain	19	1,7	50	4,6
Right Eye without pain	1093	98,3	1040	95,4
Left Eye with pain	16	1,4	50	4,6
Left Eye Without Pain	1096	98,6	1040	95,4
Right Eye with redness	9	0,8	19	1,7
Right Eye without Redness	1103	99,2	1071	98,3
Left Eye with Redness	12	1,1	19	1,7
Left Eye without Redness	1100	98,9	1071	98,3
The eye getting watery	9	0,8	38	3,5
The eye not getting watery	1103	99,2	1052	96,5
Right Eye with Burring	12	1,1	27	2,5
Right Eye Without Burring	1100	98,9	1063	97,5
Left Eye with Burring	9	0,8	27	2,5
Left Eye Without Burring	1103	99,2	1063	97,5
Eye with Color Blindness	19	1,7	26	2,4
Eye without Color Blindness	1093	98,3	1064	97,6
TOTAL	1112	100,0	1090	100

Table 3. Students' Tooth Brushing Status and Scalp Assessment

	2022-2023 Period		2023-2024 Period	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Those who brush less than 2 times a day	370	33,3	417	38,3
Those who brush 2 or more times a day	742	66,7	673	61,7
Those who brush in the mornings	771	69,3	724	66,4
Those who do not brush in the mornings	341	30,7	366	33,6
Those who brush in the afternoons	212	19,1	173	15,9
Those who do not brush in the afternoons	900	80,9	917	84,1
Those who brush in the evenings	813	73,1	869	79,7
Those who do not brush in the evenings	299	26,9	221	20,3
Those with dandruff	162	14,6	145	13,3
Those without dandruff	950	85,4	945	86,7
Those having hair loss	69	6,2	12	1,1
Those not having hair loss	1043	93,8	1078	98,9
Those having a scar on the scalp	3	0,3	14	1,3
Those not having a scar on the scalp	1109	99,7	1076	98,7
Those having lice in their hair	0	0	5	0,5
Those not having lice in their hair	1112	100	1085	99,5
TOTAL	1112	100,0	1090	100,0